

Multiport Converter Evaluation for High Penetration of Renewable Generation in Distribution Grids

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Abstract

Electrical power distribution systems are experiencing a deep penetration of renewable energy integration, which is reversing the power flow during some periods and modifying their conventional operation. In this context, the curtailment of renewable distributed generation is needed to consider the electrical limitations of transformers and lines, mainly voltage deviations and power overloads. Multiport converters with energy storage stand as a potential solution for enhancing power flow operation in the distribution system and minimising renewable generation curtailments. This paper presents an optimisation-based methodology to size multiport power converters and a techno-economic comparison to other conventional approaches. The optimisation includes energy storage components and AC power flow constraints. Moreover, specific days are considered to reduce computational requirements. This methodology is evaluated in a case study based on a medium voltage benchmark network from CIGRE to identify the best scenarios where multiport converters can be considered as a potential solution. Results conclude that the multiport converter provides clear advantages and is economically viable specially in scenarios with unbalanced distributed generation in the feeders, where their rated power is around 25 MVA, or if batteries are initially installed in the feeders.

Keywords: Multiport converters, energy storage, distribution grids,

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1. Introduction

The increase in renewable generation is transforming the conventional design and operation of the electrical grid. In particular, the penetration of renewable-based Distributed Energy Resources (DER) in the low and medium voltage grids is leading to a number of technical challenges related to overloads, voltage regulation, fault levels or power quality issues [1]. This defines the DER hosting capacity of a grid, which is the maximum amount of DER that can be integrated into a distribution grid. Conventional solutions to increase the DER hosting capacity consider the reinforcement of the existing grid with the construction of new lines and substations [2]. However, such solutions can be expensive or limited by space constraints. Alternative options are focused on increasing the flexibility of the grid by employing existing equipment. In this direction, some solutions are the readjustment of transformer tap changers, the optimal DER power operation or demand management, which are used to reduce overload or overvoltage problems [1]. Also, grid reinforcement with new equipment can be also considered. Integration of passive components such as shunt capacitors or reactors is typically employed for voltage regulation [1]. Also, storage systems can be used for limiting overloads and regulating voltage [3].

Power electronics components have an important role in improving the operation of the distribution grid. In particular, Voltage Source Converters (VSC) provide active and reactive power control, which allows reducing overloads and ensuring voltage regulation, and can operate as active filters. Power electronics are currently used in distribution grids. Renewable-based DERs, such as wind or photovoltaic generation, and battery storage are connected to the grid through VSCs. Also, DC microgrids are embedded in the distribution AC grid through AC-DC converters. Other power electronics devices have been suggested for supporting the increase of renewable generation in the distribution grid [4]. Such components are equivalent to the Flexible AC Transmission System devices used in high voltage, but the topology of the converters is mainly based on 2-level or 3-level VSCs and the functionalities that provide are different.

In particular, the so-called Soft Open Points (SOPs) have been widely studied in the literature as a solution to connect and reconfigure low-voltage

feeders of the distribution grid. The main advantages of this device compared to a simple switch are the power controllability and the firewall capability against faults [5, 6, 7]. Most of the SOP are based on a VSC back-to-back configuration [5, 7] with the possibility to connect storage in the DC link [8] or a multi-terminal configuration [9]. Also, other converter topologies are presented based on multilevel topologies [10] or matrix converters [11].

Solid State Transformers (SST) are another similar power electronics solution, where the main purpose is to replace conventional transformers interconnecting different voltage levels (both low and medium voltage) and providing additional grid support functionalities [12]. Isolated options including a dual active bridge, i.e. DC-DC converter with high-frequency transformer, are usually selected in the literature [13], but also partially isolated or non-isolated options based on back-to-back configurations can be also considered [14].

The Multiport converter (MPC) is presented as a general power electronics solution that combines the SOP and SST concepts to a larger number of terminals and functionalities. The MPC considers the possibility to integrate multiple ports with AC and DC outputs, which could be used to introduce storage or DC loads, such as electric vehicle charging stations, between AC feeders or microgrids. The MPC is expected to provide additional services for the AC and DC systems using the support of battery storage (BESS), for example, frequency support, black-start or island operation. Also, in terms of design, the MPC presents non-isolated back-to-back configurations, but also other isolated options that are expected to reduce cost and increase reliability. In [15] a MPC topology is presented with a multiwinding configuration, which ensures galvanic isolation among the ports connected through the converter.

In general, the lack of optimum design usually leads to power systems that are oversized or not properly planned, i.e. with higher costs. Modern distribution grids are complex, as they involve several generation sources, energy storage, flexible loads and power electronics components. Therefore, such distribution grids present several challenges [16] related to asset sizing, operation and economic analysis of the system. In that sense, the models used for this purpose need to balance simplicity, accuracy, precision, and data granularity [17].

1.1. Literature review

Power systems planning including power electronics components, in particular SOP, has been widely studied in the literature. In [6], soft normally open points (SNOPs) are compared to other voltage control solutions to facilitate the increase of distributed generation. The authors present an optimisation-based methodology to calculate the maximum distributed generation penetration, although no optimisation objective is used. Several networks are analysed where different SNOP placements are considered, and SNOP is rated according to the emergency power transfer capability required.

Ref. [5] compares the operational benefits of using SOPs, traditional network reconfiguration and the combination of both on a 33-bus distribution network. The authors present a methodology to minimise power loss, balance feeder load and improve voltage profile. In this case, an improved Powell's Direct Set method was developed to reduce computational requirements. Therefore, optimal SOP operation is analysed using a penalty function method to include the constraints into the objective function, i.e. an unconstrained optimisation method is considered.

Also, the optimal location and sizing of SOP has been reported in the literature. Ref. [18] studies a distribution network reconfiguration (DNR) with SOP of the 33-bus system through two multi-objective optimisation problems using the Pareto framework. The objective of both optimisation problems is load balancing and power loss minimisation, distributed generation penetration is also maximised in the DNR problem, subject to power flow and radial configuration constraints. First, DNR is solved based on the ant colony optimisation, and then, the optimal SOP rating is determined using the Taxi-cab algorithm.

A two-stage method for SOP placement and sizing is also proposed in [19]. In this case, a multi-scenario optimisation that minimises power losses and active power curtailment of distributed generation is applied on the IEEE33-bus system and a 404-bus unbalanced distribution system from Canada. In the first stage, the Loss Sensitivity Index, Voltage Deviation Index and distribution network's lateral-wise node grouping are used for SOP optimal location. And in the second stage, each SOP terminal is sized with an optimisation that includes AC power flow. MATLAB is used for SOP placement, while GAMS and CONOPT solver are used for SOP sizing. Moreover, several year-long scenarios are built to consider wind and PV power uncertainty, and the k-means clustering algorithm is used to find the representative hours that will be used in the method.

To address the non-linearity of AC power flow constraints, it is common to transform the model to a second-order cone programming (SOCP). In [20], size and location of SOPs are defined based on a relaxed optimal power flow (OPF) with network expansion costs minimisation, where voltage and current angles are eliminated from the power flow model to make it convex. The methodology is applied to the IEEE 33-bus system with different loading and wind production scenarios, and all normally open and normally closed points are considered as possible locations of SOPs.

Ref. [21] also performs a siting and sizing of SOPs with a mixed integer second-order cone programming (MISOCP). The optimisation minimises capital and annual operation costs of the SOP as well as annual energy loss cost of the distribution system considering radial distribution system constraints, and is applied to IEEE 33-bus system and a Taiwanese distribution system. The authors also use a method based on the Wasserstein distance to generate different distributed generation scenarios.

Other works focus on the operation rather than sizing of power electronics. Ref. [22] evaluates the hosting capacity of the IEEE 33 bus system with SOP using a SOCP model that maximises distributed generation installed power. Ref. [23] presents an enhanced SOCP-based method for feeder load balancing using a multi-terminal SOP on the IEEE 33-bus system. The authors propose an interval control-based strategy of the SOP where the objective is to minimise the loading deviation if the current loading exceeds a predefined threshold, otherwise the objective is to minimise only the total active power losses.

A cost-benefit analysis methodology is proposed in [24] to quantify and compare the viability of SOPs for providing different value streams by minimising the net present value. Specifically, the authors analyse the reduction of losses, renewables curtailment reduction, reliability improvement, reinforcement deferral, and congestion management for enabling flexibility services. This methodology also uses the conic optimization simplification for the OPF, and is applied in a 75-bus system.

Also, enhanced SOP configurations are discussed in the literature. In [25], converter capability charts are analysed to increase flexibility in multi-terminal converters connected in distribution networks, as changing the sizes of the individual AC-DC converter stages and connecting the AC side of those converters to electromechanical switches (multiplexers) allows its reconfiguration. Ref. [26] defines a hybrid open point (HOP) as an electromechanical switch connected in parallel with a power converter. In this case, the authors

compare the required rating of the HOP power converter against a SOP providing equivalent functionality, but voltage constraints are not considered.

Smart transformers (ST) are also presented in the literature for voltage and power flow control. Ref [27] presents an online optimization problem with AC OPF for power loss minimisation solved using genetic algorithm. This method is applied in the CIGRE LV residential distribution network connected to MVAC grid through ST to generate active and reactive power references for distributed generation converters. A similar methodology is presented in [28] to determine the active power references of distributed generation converters as well as scheduling of EVs and BESS, and load shedding if needed, in a ST based islanded microgrid.

On the other hand, energy management capabilities are important to be considered during planning, specially if storage is included, as it can have a significant impact on operating cost reduction and renewable energy penetration. An economic energy management of grid-connected flexible energy hubs that aims to minimise the operating cost subject to networks optimal power flow is presented in [29]. The system includes renewables and storage devices for both electrical and heating networks. The unscented transformation method has been used to manage uncertainty regarding demand, renewable generation, and price of electrical and heating energy.

Ref. [30] presents the sizing of a hybrid renewable islanded system including electrical and thermal energy. The system contains wind power, bio-waste units as a combined heat and power generator, compressed air energy storage, power electronic converters, and smart charging electric vehicles. The objective is to minimise annual capital and maintenance costs of the elements subject to their operation, but network OPF is not considered. In this case, the point estimate method has been used to model the uncertainty related to load, wind speed, bio-waste gas flow, and electric vehicle parameters.

Table 1 presents a summary of the literature discussed in this section.

Table 1: Literature review summary

Ref.	Power electronics components	Sizing	Min power loss	Load balancing	Max hosting capacity	Min curtailment	PV	Wind power	Power flow constraints
[5]	SOP		✓	✓					penalty function
[6]	SNOP								no current constraints
[18]	SOP	✓	✓	✓					
[19]	SOP	✓	✓			✓		✓	AC PF
[20]	SOP	✓	✓				✓	✓	SOCP
[21]	SOP	✓	✓				✓	✓	MISOCP
[22]	SOP				✓		✓		SOCP
[23]	multi-terminal SOP		✓	✓					SOCP
[24]	SOP		✓			✓			SOCP

1.2. Research gaps

Soft open points are usually used in the literature to improve distribution network operation, as shown in Table 1. In addition, a number of software tools, including open-source options such as MATPOWER [31] and GridCal [32], are employed for power systems planning. However, the representation of multiport converters has not been considered yet.

When studying SOPs, it is common to use power flow simplifications to avoid non-linear optimisations, usually through the SOCP. Compared with existing literature, the methodology proposed in this paper is based on a non-linear and non-convex AC OPF and includes Multiport converters' sizing considering several grid operation conditions.

PV and wind power DER are usually studied together with SOP, but a research gap is found in combined benefits of SOP and BESS. A comparison between SOP and BESS improvements in renewables curtailment is also performed in this paper.

1.3. Contribution

This paper analyses and evaluates the application of the multiport converter in distribution grids with high penetration of renewable generation. In particular, the contributions of this paper are illustrated in Fig. 1 and are summarised as follows:

- Presenting a general methodology to size the multiport converter and provide a techno-economical analysis with specific indicators.
- Comparing the multiport converter with other conventional options as a solution to reduce the renewable generation curtailment.

The methodology is based on an optimisation that includes energy storage components and AC power flow constraints. The main objective of this optimisation is to minimise the multiport converter costs and renewables' curtailment. Moreover, specific days are considered instead of a full year to reduce computational requirements, also storage sizing is set as a known parameter in the optimisation. In that sense, a clustering method and a storage sizing method are presented as optional steps previous to the multiport sizing, although other algorithms can also be used.

The methodology and multiport converter evaluation are validated in a case study adapted from the medium voltage CIGRE benchmark network. A sensitivity analysis of different components and generation distribution is considered to understand the multiport converter advantages. Then, general conclusions are obtained about the potential application and feasibility of multiport converters for distribution grids.

Figure 1: Framework of the general methodology

2. Enhancing distribution grids with multiport converters

The introduction of multiport converters improves flexibility, controllability and resilience of distribution grids. In terms of flexibility and controllability, power flows can be controlled to improve grid efficiency, provide grid services and prevent line and transformer overloads or excessive voltage variations. In terms of resilience, island operation and black-start can be ensured for specific areas of the distribution grid. Multiport converters can be also distributed in different locations to increase grid reliability.

Multiport converters for LV and MV distribution grids present differences, especially in terms of the topologies that are considered. In LV applications, AC-DC converters can be combined in a common DC bus. However, in MV applications converters with multiwinding configurations are preferred to ensure isolation between the terminals. This paper considers the analysis of multiport converters in MV distribution grids. Fig.2 represents an example of a MV distribution grid with two multiport converters.

Figure 2: Example of MV distribution grid with multiport converters.

The utilization of multiport converters can contribute to facilitate the massive integration of distributed renewable generation while enhancing the connection of several loads and other equipment. This converter enables the interconnection of multiple electrical grids and equipment in AC or DC and considers different voltage or frequency levels, number of phases or grounding schemes. Therefore, the overall number of power electronics for renewable generation or grid support can be reduced. In particular, this converter can combine the advantages of energy storage and other grid support equipment and implement an integrated solution.

The installation of multiport converters requires an additional investment in the distribution network that must be compensated with an economic return. Multiport converters could provide services that generate an income. Also, such converters can enable additional generation that is curtailed due to grid operation constraints, such as line overloads or excessive bus voltage variations.

Scenarios with high penetration of renewable generation are considered in this paper to explore the advantages of a multiport converter. In such scenarios, renewable generation is likely to be curtailed due to a limited line or transformer power capacity. Therefore, a multiport converter could be used to maximize the line and transformer capacity factor and reduce the generation curtailment.

3. General Methodology

This section presents a methodology to size multiport converters used to interconnect MV feeders with storage. Economical and technical indicators are provided to evaluate the advantages of installing a multiport converter. These indicators can be also employed to compare different interconnection configurations. In addition, a clustering method and a storage sizing method can be included as optional steps previous to the multiport sizing.

Fig. 3 shows a flowchart of the general methodology, where three main steps are considered: representative days selection, storage sizing, and multiport converter sizing. Generation and demand profiles for a year are provided with hourly resolution. The technical parameters of the grid and the assets contained in the system are also needed. Moreover, cost parameters of the grid reinforcements such as storage and several interconnection options must be provided, as well as the operation costs of the connection to the external grid. As a result, several economical and technical indicators are provided to

evaluate the advantages of installing a multiport converter. These indicators can be also employed to compare different interconnection configurations.

Figure 3: Flowchart of the general methodology

This methodology has been specifically developed to study a multiport converter used to interconnect MV feeders with renewable generation and energy storage. Although it can be used also on other systems including MV or LV distribution networks, microgrids, and buildings.

The central part of this methodology is the multiport converter sizing, which consists of an optimisation problem. However, if the inputs were directly given to the optimisation problem, the optimisation would be too complex and computationally infeasible to solve with the available resources. For this reason, the optimisation is divided into three steps, simplifying the optimisation problem.

3.1. Representative days selection

To reduce the amount of data, the idea of clusters has been used. Therefore, considering only specific days instead of a 1-year time which is typically

used in planning optimisation.

The methodology proposed considers the annual load and generation profiles as shown in Fig. 4. As a result, each representative day has a weight w_{day} according to its predominance for a year. The heuristic method is detailed in Appendix D has been used. However, other several clustering or classification algorithms and software could be considered to improve the representative days' selection.

Figure 4: Flowchart of the representative days' selection methodology

3.2. Storage sizing

If storage is included in the feeders, the required energy capacity and power are defined before the multiport converter sizing. It is assumed that batteries are used as a storage solution, but other options could be also considered. Batteries can be sized based on different requirements and through different methods. The methodology used to size the storage is explained below, although other methodologies can also be considered.

In this paper, the batteries are sized to ensure island operation. Therefore, in case the feeders are disconnected from the main grid, island operation must be ensured for a specific time period. In particular, the battery sizing is defined based on the power and energy required during the periods with lack of generation in the system.

Hourly load and generation profiles for a year are employed, but grid constraints are not considered. Then, the net power exchange for each h hour is defined as:

$$P_h = \sum_i P_{d-i,h} - P_{g-i,h} \quad \forall h \quad (1)$$

where $P_{d-i,h}$ and $P_{g-i,h}$ are the demand and generation powers for each node i .

Then, the net energy exchange for a period of H hours starting at hour t is defined as:

$$E_{H,t} = \sum_{h=t}^{t+H} P_h \quad (2)$$

When $E_{H,t}$ is positive the feeders require additional energy to supply the demand that must be provided by the storage. When $E_{H,t}$ is negative the feeders have a generation excess that can be used to charge the storage. Next year is supposed to have the same profile.

The battery sizing only considers periods where P_h and $E_{H,t}$ are positive. The battery power P_{bat0} and storage E_{st0} must cover all cases, and are expressed as:

$$P_{bat0} = \max(P_1, \dots, P_{Nh}) \quad (3)$$

$$E_{st0} = \max(E_{H,1}, \dots, E_{H,Nh}) \quad (4)$$

where $Nh = 8760$ is the number of hours in a year.

At this point, the battery is sized to be able to cover 100% of the cases, including the worst possible scenario. As a result, the battery could be excessively high and oversized in the majority of situations. Then, a value between 90 and 100% is considered to reduce the battery size, i.e. the battery cost. Therefore, the battery power P_{bat} and storage required E_{st} are defined such that a percentage of the total number of cases with positive $E_{H,t}$ are covered.

Finally, the battery capacity E_{cap} is defined as:

$$E_{cap} = \frac{E_{st}}{DoD} \quad (5)$$

where DoD is the depth of discharge

3.3. Multiport converter sizing

The nominal power of the multiport converter terminals is determined with an optimisation that considers hourly load and generation profiles and the grid constraints. As mentioned before, full-year optimisation has high computational requirements. Therefore, several representative days are considered. In that sense, the proposed optimisation considers separate submodels, one for each representative day. Each submodel will include all system

components and their constraints. To combine all the submodels in the main optimisation model, some additional constraints are needed. On the one hand, the sizing variables must be common on all days. On the other hand, energetic variables and indicators that represent the whole year are estimated to be the weighted sum of the representative days selected.

Different elements can be included in the optimisation: the grid, renewable generators, battery storage, and multiport converter. Also, loads are defined as steady-state PQ loads, and the connection of the system to the external grid consists of a simplified model characterised by the power exchange between the system and the external grid. Each of those elements is modelled separately with a set of variables and constraints, and all the models are interconnected.

The objective function, variables and constraints of the optimisation are shown below. As a result, multiport converter size and optimal system operation are obtained, as well as some economical and technical indicators.

3.3.1. Objective function

The multiport converter is introduced to improve feeders' operation without an excessive additional cost. The optimisation will minimise the multiport converter cost while optimising other indicators depending on the case study.

This methodology can be applied to a wide range of scenarios. In scenarios with high penetration of renewable generation, the generation is likely to be curtailed due to a limited line or transformer capacity. And the multiport converter could be used to maximise the line and transformer capacity factor and reduce the generation curtailment. Therefore, the optimisation will minimise generation curtailment, i.e. maximising feeders' operation income due to additional generation enabled by the multiport converter.

Moreover, some minor terms can also need to be added to the objective function to obtain a correct optimisation performance. A usual reason for needing this term is to avoid using binary variables to relate two opposite variables.

As a result, the objective function can be expressed as:

$$[\min] C_{MPC} - I_{ren} \cdot t_{life} + \text{other} \quad (6)$$

where C_{MPC} is the multiport converter cost, I_{ren} is the annual income from renewable generation and t_{life} is a factor to weight the two main terms supposed as 30 years, which is similar to the multiport converter lifetime. The

expressions of C_{MPC} and I_{ren} are presented in Chapter 3.3.5 and 3.3.6 respectively. *other* represents the additional minor term that may be needed, which is formulated in Chapter 3.3.7.

3.3.2. Grid model

The system grid is modelled as steady-state with variables defined for each electrical node i and for each hour t of the considered representative days d . Grid variables include active and reactive power injected ($p_{i,t,d}$ and $q_{i,t,d}$), voltage phase and magnitude ($\delta_{V_{i,t,d}}$ and $v_{i,t,d}$), and line current ($i_{i,k,t,d}$) between nodes i, k . All these variables are expressed per unit, except the phases, which are expressed in degrees.

The grid constraints are related to:

- Voltage magnitude limits:

$$v_{min,i} \leq v_{i,t,d} \leq v_{max,i} \quad (7)$$

where $v_{min,i}$ and $v_{max,i}$ are supposed as $\pm 10\%$ of the nominal value, following the Standard EN 50160 [33].

- The main grid is supposed to be the slack. Therefore, the voltage magnitude and angle of the main grid node are fixed at 1 p.u. and 0° respectively, for all hours t and all days d .
- AC power flow equations to ensure active and reactive power balance:

$$p_{i,t,d} = v_{i,t,d} \cdot \sum_k v_{k,t,d} \cdot \left(G_{i,k} \cdot \cos(\delta_{V_{i,t,d}} - \delta_{V_{k,t,d}}) + B_{i,k} \cdot \sin(\delta_{V_{i,t,d}} - \delta_{V_{k,t,d}}) \right) \quad \forall i, t, d \quad (8)$$

$$q_{i,t,d} = v_{i,t,d} \cdot \sum_k v_{k,t,d} \cdot \left(G_{i,k} \cdot \sin(\delta_{V_{i,t,d}} - \delta_{V_{k,t,d}}) + B_{i,k} \cdot \cos(\delta_{V_{i,t,d}} - \delta_{V_{k,t,d}}) \right) \quad \forall i, t, d \quad (9)$$

where $G_{i,k}$ and $B_{i,k}$ are the real and imaginary part of the grid admittance matrix (Y_{bus}) at nodes i, k expressed per unit.

- Line current limits. The current of each line is calculated and its maximum value is limited. The current can be expressed as (11), but this expression is reformulated as (12) to avoid complex numbers.

$$\underline{v}_{i,t,d} = v_{i,t,d} \cdot (\cos \delta_{V_{i,t,d}} + j \sin \delta_{V_{i,t,d}}) \quad (10)$$

$$\underline{i}_{i,k,t,d} = (\underline{v}_{i,t,d} - \underline{v}_{k,t,d}) \cdot \frac{1}{z_{i,k}} - \underline{v}_{i,t,d} \cdot \frac{y_{i,k}}{2} \quad (11)$$

$$i_{i,k,t,d}^2 = \frac{v_{i,t,d}^2 + v_{k,t,d}^2 - 2 \cdot v_{i,t,d} \cdot v_{k,t,d} \cdot \cos \delta_{V_{k,t,d}} - \delta_{V_{i,t,d}}}{z_{i,k}^2} - \frac{y_{i,k} \cdot v_{i,t,d} \cdot v_{k,t,d} \cdot \cos \delta_{y_{i,k}} + \delta_{V_{i,t,d}} + \delta_{z_{i,k}} - \delta_{V_{k,t,d}}}{z_{i,k}} \quad (12)$$

$$+ \frac{y_{i,k} \cdot v_{i,t,d}^2 \cdot \cos \delta_{z_{i,k}} + \delta_{y_{i,k}}}{z_{i,k}} + \frac{y_{i,k}^2 \cdot v_{i,t,d}^2}{4} \quad \forall i, k, t, d$$

$$i_{i,k,t,d}^2 \leq i_{max-i,k}^2 \quad \forall i, k, t, d \quad (13)$$

where $i_{max-i,k}$ is the current limit of the line between nodes i, k , $z_{i,k}$ and $y_{i,k}$ are line impedance and admittance magnitude expressed per unit, and $\delta_{z_{i,k}}$ and $\delta_{y_{i,k}}$ are their respective phases expressed in degrees.

3.3.3. Generator model

The generators of this problem are supposed to be from renewable sources, meaning PV and wind power, although conventional generators can also be considered. PV and wind power are defined as PQ steady-state generators, with variables related to their operation. Therefore, including active and reactive power generated ($p_{g,i,t,d}$ and $q_{g,i,t,d}$), which are defined for each generator g connected to the node i and for each hour t of the considered representative days d . All these variables are expressed per unit.

The generator constraints are related to:

- Generation curtailment. The active power provided by each renewable generator is positive and limited by the maximum available power from the generation profiles. Then, the active power generation limits are expressed as;

$$0 \leq p_{g,i,t,d} \leq p_{max-g,i,t,d} \quad \forall g, i, t, d \quad (14)$$

where $p_{max-g,i,t,d}$ is the maximum available power from the generator g connected to the node i at hour t of the day d

- Generator current limits. As generators are connected to the grid through VSC, they can exchange reactive power. But the total power is limited by a maximum current, which can be expressed as:

$$p_{g,i,t,d}^2 + q_{g,i,t,d}^2 \leq (v_{i,t,d} \cdot i_{max-g,i})^2 \quad \forall g, i, t, d \quad (15)$$

$$i_{max-g,i} = \frac{s_{max-g,i}}{v_{n-i}} \quad \forall g, i \quad (16)$$

$$s_{max-g,i} = \frac{p_{n-g,i}}{PF_{g,i}} \quad \forall g, i \quad (17)$$

where v_{n-i} is the nominal voltage supposed as 1, $PF_{g,i}$ is the power factor, and $p_{n-g,i}$ is the nominal active power of the generator. A 44 % reactive power capability is considered, according to IEEE Standard 1547 [34], using Equation (17) with a power factor of 0.915.

3.3.4. Battery storage model

BESS is modelled as steady-state with variables also related to the operation, as batteries are supposed to be sized previously to the optimisation. Therefore, BESS variables are defined for each battery b connected to the node i for each hour t of the considered representative days d . They include active charging and discharging powers ($p_{char-b,i,t,d}$ and $p_{disch-b,i,t,d}$), reactive power exchanged ($q_{b,i,t,d}$), and the state of charge ($SOC_{b,i,t,d}$). All these variables are expressed per unit.

The BEES constraints are related to:

- Charging and discharging power limits, which are expressed as:

$$0 \leq p_{char-b,i,t,d} \leq p_{n-b,i} \quad \forall b, i, t, d \quad (18)$$

$$0 \leq p_{disch-b,i,t,d} \leq p_{n-b,i} \quad \forall b, i, t, d \quad (19)$$

where $p_{n-b,i}$ is the nominal active power of the battery b connected to the node i .

- State of charge (SOC) limits, which are expressed as:

$$SOC_{min-b,i} \leq SOC_{b,i,t,d} \leq SOC_{max-b,i} \quad \forall b, i, t, d \quad (20)$$

where $SOC_{min-b,i}$ and $SOC_{max-b,i}$ are minimum and maximum SOC values, supposed as 0.2 and 1 according to manufacturer recommendations [3].

- SOC calculation, which is expressed as:

$$SOC_{b,i,t,d} = SOC_{b,i,t-1,d} \cdot (1 - \tau_{bat}) + \left(p_{char-b,i,t,d} \cdot \eta_{char} + \frac{p_{disch-b,i,t,d}}{\eta_{disch}} \right) \cdot S_b \cdot \frac{\Delta t}{E_{cap-b,i}} \quad \forall b, i, t, d \quad (21)$$

where τ_{bat} is the energy loss ratio supposed as 0.001 [3], η_{ch} and η_{disch} are the charging and discharging efficiencies both supposed as 0.9 [3], S_b is the base power of the system, and Δt is the calculation period, which is 1 h.

- Daily SOC level. The SOC must be the same at the beginning and the end of each representative day to ensure that the battery has a cycling operation. Moreover, the SOC at the beginning of the day is unknown. This can be expressed as:

$$SOC_{b,i,t=0,d} = SOC_{b,i,t=24,d} \quad \forall b, i, d \quad (22)$$

- Battery converter current limits. If the battery is directly connected to the multiport, the connection is in DC and this constraint is not applied. But if the battery is connected to the grid, a VSC is used. Therefore it can exchange reactive power with a limit of maximum current, which can be expressed as:

$$(p_{char-b,i,t,d} - p_{disch-b,i,t,d})^2 + q_{b,i,t,d}^2 \leq (v_{i,t,d} \cdot i_{max-b,i})^2 \quad \forall b, i, t, d \quad (23)$$

$$i_{max-b,i} = \frac{s_{max-b,i}}{v_{n-i}} \quad \forall b, i \quad (24)$$

$$s_{max-b,i} = \frac{p_{n-b,i}}{PF_{b,i}} \quad \forall b, i \quad (25)$$

where $PF_{b,i}$ is the power factor. A 44 % reactive power capability is considered, according to IEEE Standard 1547 [34], using Equation (25) with a power factor of 0.915.

3.3.5. Multiport converter model

Multiport converter is modelled as steady-state with variables related to both the operation and sizing of the converter. Operation variables are defined for each multiport converter terminal k connected to the node i for each hour t of the considered representative days d . They include the active and reactive powers exchanged by the multiport converter terminal, $p_{MPC-k,i,t,d}$ and $q_{MPC-k,i,t,d}$. On the other hand, this sizing variable is the nominal power of each multiport converter terminal connected to the node i ($s_{n,MPC-k,i}$). This variable is expressed as the maximum apparent power considering all hourly powers exchanged by the converter terminal. All these variables are expressed per unit.

The multiport converter constraints are related to:

- Multiport converter power balance. This must be ensured considering active powers exchanged by each converter terminal, including if a centralised battery is introduced as an additional terminal of the MPC. Therefore, active power balance within a multiport converter is expressed as:

$$\sum_{k,i} p_{MPC-k,i,t,d} = 0 \quad \forall t, d \quad (26)$$

- Multiport current limits, which are expressed as:

$$p_{MPC-k,i,t,d}^2 + q_{MPC-k,i,t,d}^2 \leq (v_{i,t,d} \cdot i_{max,MPC-k,i})^2 \quad \forall k, i, t, d \quad (27)$$

$$i_{max,MPC-k,i} = \frac{s_{n,MPC-k,i}}{v_{n-i}} \quad \forall k, i \quad (28)$$

- Reactive power limits. According to IEEE Standard 1547 [34], energy storage DER should be capable of exchanging reactive power with a minimum capability of ± 44 %. As the multiport presented in this paper is planned to work together with ESS, it has been limited the reactive power following the same capability curve. If this constraint was not considered, reactive power would increase a lot the multiport converter's nominal apparent power. Therefore, the reactive power limits are expressed as:

$$q_{MPC-k,i,t,d} \leq 0.44 \cdot s_{n,MPC-k,i} \quad \forall k, i, t, d \quad (29)$$

$$-q_{MPC-k,i,t,d} \leq 0.44 \cdot s_{n,MPC-k,i} \quad \forall k, i, t, d \quad (30)$$

- Cost of the multiport converter, expressed as:

$$C_{MPC} = \sum_{k,i} C_{conv-k} \cdot s_{n,MPC-k,i} \cdot S_b \quad (31)$$

where C_{conv-k} is the unitary cost of the multiport converter terminal k , supposed as 150 €/kVA [3].

3.3.6. Technical and economic indicators

In addition to the previous models, some technical and economic indicators have been defined to analyse the results and set the objective function. The technical indicators considered are:

- Annual renewable generation (E_{ren}) which is expressed as:

$$E_{ren} = \frac{1}{\sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d} \cdot \sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d \cdot \sum_{t=0}^{23} \sum_{g,i} p_{g,i,t,d} \cdot S_b \cdot \Delta t \quad (32)$$

where N_d is the number of representative days, w_d is the weight of each representative day in the year.

- Renewable generation curtailment (E_{curt}). Due to grid constraints or converter power limits, the generators may not produce as much energy as is available. The curtailment represents the percentage of renewable generation reduction with respect to the maximum available for a year. This can be expressed as:

$$E_{curt} = \frac{E_{ren-max} - E_{ren}}{E_{ren-max}} \cdot 100 \quad (33)$$

$$E_{ren-max} = \frac{1}{\sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d} \cdot \sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d \cdot \sum_{t=0}^{23} \sum_{g,i} p_{max-g,i,t,d} \cdot S_b \cdot \Delta t$$

The economic indicators considered are:

- Investment (C_T). This represents the cost of additional equipment installed in the feeders, which mainly considers multiport converter costs (C_{MPC}). Also, costs from batteries [3] (C_{bat}) or other equipment (C_{oth}) can be included. Then, the total investment cost can be expressed as:

$$C_T = C_{MPC} + C_{bat} + C_{oth} \quad (34)$$

$$C_{baty} = \sum_k \left(S_{n,bat-k} \cdot C_{conv} + \frac{E_{cap-k}}{\eta_{ch} \cdot \eta_{disch}} \cdot C_{cap} \right) \quad (35)$$

where C_{conv} is the converter cost in €/kVA, C_{cap} is the energy storage cost in €/kWh.

- Annual income from renewable generation (I_{ren}), which is expressed as:

$$I_{ren} = C_{en} \cdot E_{ren} \quad (36)$$

where C_{en} is the average annual energy price in €/kWh.

- Payback time respect an initial base configuration (PBT). This is the period to recover the initial investment based on additional income from the feeders' operation. Then, the payback time is expressed as:

$$PBT = \frac{C_T}{C_{en} \cdot (E_{ren} - E_{ren-bc})} \quad (37)$$

where E_{ren-bc} is the annual renewable generation in the base configuration. This indicator is especially useful to compare multiport converter solutions or alternative interconnection configurations.

3.3.7. Other variables and constraints

Besides the model of each component, to build the system it is needed to connect the elements. In that sense, active and reactive power balance must be done, expressed as:

$$p_{i,t,d} = -p_{load-i,t,d} + \sum_{MG} (p_{buy-MG,i,t,d} - p_{sell-MG,i,t,d}) + \sum_g p_{g,i,t,d} + \sum_b (p_{disch-b,i,t,d} + p_{char-b,i,t,d}) + \sum_k p_{MPC-k,i,t,d} \quad \forall i, t, d \quad (38)$$

$$q_{i,t,d} = -q_{load-i,t,d} + \sum_{MG} q_{MG,i,t,d} + \sum_g q_{g,i,t,d} - \sum_b q_{b,i,t,d} + \sum_k q_{MPC-k,i,t,d} \quad \forall i, t, d \quad (39)$$

where, for each hour t of the considered representative day d , $p_{load-i,t,d}$ and $q_{load-i,t,d}$ are the active and reactive power load at node i , $p_{buy-g,i,t,d}$ and

$p_{sell-g,i,t,d}$ are the active power bought and sold to the main grid MG connected to the node i , and $q_{MG,i,t,d}$ is the reactive power exchanged with the main grid MG connected to the node i .

Additionally, some terms need to be added to the objective function to obtain a correct optimisation performance. With the current optimisation, some mathematical solutions would not have physical sense. On the one hand, the battery cannot charge and discharge at the same time. These variables have been defined separately because of the efficiencies but they are opposite. On the other hand, the energy exchanged between the main grid and each feeder is also defined with two opposite variables, power bought and sold, which cannot occur at the same time. One way to solve this situation would be to relate the opposite variables with an auxiliary binary variable, but this will result in a high computational cost. Instead, it is decided to implement an equivalent in the objective function. The sum of the variable pairs is minimised to achieve that when one variable has some value, its opposite will be 0. Moreover, to relate this term with the main optimisation objective it is required to apply some coefficient, so it will not affect the overall results. This coefficient is supposed as 0.00001. Therefore, the additional optimisation term can be expressed as:

$$\text{other} = 0.00001 \cdot (\text{other}_{BESS} + \text{other}_{MG}) \quad (40)$$

$$\text{other}_{BESS} = \sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d \cdot \sum_{b,i} \sum_{t=0}^{23} (p_{char-b,i,t,d} + p_{disch-b,i,t,d}) \quad (41)$$

$$\text{other}_{MG} = \sum_{d=1}^{N_d} w_d \cdot \sum_{MG,i} \sum_{t=0}^{23} (p_{buy-MG,i,t,d} - p_{sell-MG,i,t,d}) \quad (42)$$

4. Evaluation of multiport converter configurations

Multiport converter configurations are analysed based on the methodology presented in the previous section and considering a case study with different scenarios. The results are aimed to provide a general conclusion about the application of multiport converters in feeders with high penetration of renewable distributed resources.

4.1. Case study

The case study is based on the European MV distribution network from the CIGRE Task Force C6.04.02 [35]. The feeder's nominal voltage is 20 kV and the system frequency is 50 Hz. The network configuration and parameters are the same as in the CIGRE benchmark model.

This benchmark network has two feeders (indicated as A and B in Fig. 5) which are optionally interconnected with switches in three locations. Multiport converters are usually located in nearby buses or where there are already switches or other interconnection equipment. For this reason, in this case, only the interconnection between buses 16-17 is considered with the possibility to employ a multiport converter instead of a switch, as shown in Fig. 5. This is also a typical location used to interconnect feeders. Batteries can be distributed at each feeder or centralised as an additional multiport terminal.

Figure 5: Electrical scheme of case study with multiport converter

The network parameters considered for the lines and transformers in the different configurations are explained in Appendix A. Load and generation units are distributed in the buses as shown in Fig. 5. The hourly profiles are based on information from a region of Spain, loads and generation are defined as explained in Appendix B and Appendix C respectively.

The generation distribution may have an important impact on the results. Therefore, three different scenarios are studied, which represent potential situations to evaluate the advantage of interconnecting feeders:

- Scenario 1. Similar solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind capacity power are installed in Feeders A and B.
- Scenario 2. Wind generation is mainly installed in Feeder A, while PV generation is mainly located in Feeder B.
- Scenario 3. Most of the generation capacity is installed in Feeder A.

More details of these generation scenarios are presented in Appendix C. In total, the average load is 20 MW and the average generation capacity is 45 MW. Then, the representative days considered later in the optimisation are obtained applying the method from Section 3.1, the load and generation profiles of these days are presented in Appendix D.

4.2. Configuration definition

A number of configurations are defined based on MPC options, but also considering other possibilities, such as direct switch connection or different battery distributions. Three MPC options are considered: MPC without battery, MPC with converter-connected battery and MPC with direct-connected battery. This last option does not include a controllable terminal for the battery to reduce costs. The MPC configurations are compared to a base configuration without feeder interconnection and a configuration with a switch connection. Also, the introduction of distributed or centralised batteries is compared.

Then, eight configurations are defined based on the previous considerations:

- Ref: reference configuration with two separated feeders without batteries.

- DB: two separated feeders and distributed batteries, which are sized for island requirements.
- DB-S: feeders with direct switch connection and distributed batteries.
- DB-MPC: feeders with a two-terminal MPC connection and distributed batteries.
- CB-MPC3, CB-MPC3f and CB-MPC2: feeders with a three-terminal MPC connection and a centralised battery. In CB-MPC3, the battery is introduced as an additional controllable terminal of the MPC, and that third terminal is sized in the optimisation. In CB-MPC3f, the battery is introduced as an additional controllable terminal of the MPC, but the third terminal has the same size as the battery’s nominal power. In CB-MPC2, the battery is introduced as an additional terminal of the MPC, but with a direct connection to the DC bus.
- MPC: feeders with a two-terminal MPC connection without batteries, where the MPC acts as a soft open point.

A sensitivity analysis with the parameters of Table 2 is performed to provide a general conclusion. Scenarios with 25 % and 50 % reduction of installed generation capacity are also analysed.

Table 2: Sensitivity analysis parameters

Parameters	Base value	Additional values
Island time for battery size	2 h	1, 3 h
Energy storage cost	750 €/kWh [3]	650, 800 €/kWh
Converter cost	150 €/kVA [3]	140, 160 €/kVA
Annual energy price	50 €/MWh [36]	20, 100, 150 €/MWh

4.3. Battery sizing

The batteries are sized based on a requirement of island mode following the method presented in Section 3.2. In particular, the batteries are sized to cover a ratio of 99 % of the cases that can operate 2h in island mode. For example, Fig. 6 shows the ratio of cases for scenario 2 and a centralised battery, which results in $E_{cap} = 48.27$ kWh and represents a battery capacity reduction of around 37 % compared to a ratio of 100 % of the cases. Appendix

E and Table 3 summarise the energy capacity and active power required for the batteries in each scenario and considering distributed or centralised options. It is clear that sharing a centralised battery between the two feeders results in lower total energy capacity and power, especially in scenarios 2 and 3. For example, in Table 3, the energy capacity of the centralised battery is 0.5 % less than the distributed one in scenario 1, while this reduction is 8.4 % in scenario 2 and 3.1 % in scenario 3.

Figure 6: Ratio of total battery capacity required to cover 2h in island mode for scenario 2 and centralised battery option

Table 3: Battery sizing results for 2h island mode

	Distributed				Centralised	
	P_A [MW]	$E_{cap,A}$ [MWh]	P_B [MW]	$E_{cap,B}$ [MWh]	P_{A+B} [MW]	$E_{cap,A+B}$ [MWh]
Scenario 1	12.12	33.39	6.06	16.49	17.97	49.67
Scenario 2	11.27	30.54	8.63	23.67	17.97	49.67
Scenario 3	10.78	29.41	7.62	20.9	17.73	48.74

4.4. Multiport converter sizing

The results related to the MPC size are analysed for all the scenarios and compared among the different configuration options. Concerning the sensitivity analysis, all the parameters in Table 2 are considered, except for the energy storage cost. This is because this cost is not included in the objective function (6), i.e. the optimisation results are not affected.

Regarding the sizing results, the rated power of the MPC terminals has low variability in scenarios 2 and 3 (Fig. 7a). The terminals without battery

are sized based on the optimisation presented in Section 3.3 and the resulting rated power is around 25 MVA, which is the nominal power of the lines and transformers. This happens because the currents saturate the lines and transformers, which will be further explained in Section 4.5.

The terminal with a centralised battery can be sized based on the method in Section 3.2. In this case, the active power is around 18 MW, as shown in Table 3 and Appendix E. But this terminal can also be sized in the optimisation presented in Section 3.3. When optimised, the size of this terminal is lower than the battery's nominal power (Fig. 7b). For example, the optimised power is in the range of 7-14 MW whereas in Table 3 and Appendix E the power range is 17-19 MW. This happens because there is no requirement for island operation in the optimisation, so the battery from Table 3 and Appendix E is oversized for normal operation.

Figure 7: Boxplot of $S_{n,MPC-k}$ for terminals without battery (a) and the battery terminal (b) considering all scenarios, configurations, and sensitivity parameters of Table 2

In scenario 1, the rated power of the MPC terminals without battery has a lot of variability. Fig. 8 shows that the energy price seems the most sensitive parameter, followed by the network configuration. The MPC size decreases when the energy price is low, and it tends to 25 MVA when the energy price increases.

Figure 8: $S_{n,MPC-k}$ for terminals without battery in scenario 1 considering all configurations and sensitivity parameters of Table 2

However, the highest variability in MPC sizing is found when changing the generation installed capacity, which is shown in Fig. 9. As a general trend, the rated power of the MPC terminals is reduced when the generation capacity is also reduced. This is very clear in scenarios 1 and 2, where the power may reach zero making the multiport converter not a possible option to reduce renewable generation curtailment. In scenario 3, due to its generation distribution, the generation has to be reduced a lot to observe a MPC size reduction defined by the optimisation. The terminal with a centralised battery in the configuration CB-MPC3f does not follow this trend because its size is equal to the nominal power of the battery, which is higher with lower generation to be able to fulfil the island operation request.

(a) Scenario 1

(b) Scenario 2

(c) Scenario 3

Figure 9: $S_{n,MPC-k}$ for all terminals with Base generation capacity and with 25 and 50 % reduction

4.5. Operation analysis

Taking a closer look at the results regarding the operation of the system, it can be seen where the problems or limitations appear and how the multiport converter contributes to improve the system performance. For this analysis, the representative day 10 of scenario 2 has been chosen and CB-MPC3 configuration has been compared with the Reference one, base values of Table 2 have been considered. This case is an example, but similar results are observed in other days and scenarios.

In the Reference configuration, the voltage throughout the day is around 1 on most of the buses, while the currents saturate in all lines of feeder B and have a peak of around 15h in some lines of feeder A. For this reason, the multiport converter tends to have the same nominal power as the lines and transformers in this scenario and configuration, as the MPC tries to redistribute the currents. The multiport converter has a significant impact as the voltages tend to increase in most buses, especially during the mid-day. However, an off-peak in the buses of feeder B is observed around 15h, as can be seen in Fig. 10. Fig. 11 shows that the currents also tend to increase during the mid-day with the introduction of the MPC, where more lines get saturated including the ones connecting to the main grid.

Figure 10: Buses voltage of scenario 2 with Reference and CB-MPC3 configurations in representative day 10 considering the base values of Table 2

Figure 11: Lines current of scenario 2 with configurations Ref and CB-MPC3 in representative day 10 considering the base values of Table 2

4.6. Technical analysis

The annual renewable generation presents significant variations depending on the scenarios, configuration options and battery size. Fig. 12a shows the results considering the base values of Table 2, but equivalent results can be obtained for the additional values of the sensitivity analysis. It should be mentioned that low variability on the rated power of the MPC terminals, present in scenarios 2 and 3, will lead to limited effect of the parameter variations on the annual generation.

As expected, battery introduction improves the annual generation, with an increase of more than 5 % of DB compared to Ref, as seen in Fig. 12b. Feeder interconnection with switch or MPC also contributes to the annual generation, especially in scenarios with unbalanced generation with increases of 15-20 % in scenario 2 and 25-30 % in scenario 3, as seen in Figure 12b. Annual generation increase is directly related to a curtailment reduction, as observed in Fig. 13, since high penetration of renewable generation im-

plies significant curtailment in all scenarios due to lines and transformers' saturation.

(a)

(b)

Figure 12: Annual generation (a) and Annual generation increase from Ref configuration (b) for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 2

Figure 13: Curtailment for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 2

In addition, a comparison between battery and feeder interconnection options is shown in Fig. 14 to understand which is the most convenient option in scenarios with high penetration of renewable generation. It is clear that when the generation is unbalanced (scenarios 2 and 3), feeder interconnection with switch or MPC (DB-S and DB-MPC options) presents a higher increase in annual generation compared to a battery capacity increase (1h and 3h island options). However, when the generation is uniformly distributed (scenario 1), increasing the battery capacity can have the same impact on annual generation as interconnections with switch or MPC. It should be also mentioned that the cost of battery capacity is significantly more expensive than the cost of interconnection equipment. Therefore, the interconnection options are preferred compared to increasing battery capacity.

Figure 14: Annual generation for each scenario comparing some configurations

4.7. Economic analysis

The economic analysis presents the investment C_T and payback time PBT evaluation on the case study to further compare the different configuration options and understand when the MPC is a convenient solution.

Regarding the investment, battery cost represents a significant part of the total cost, while the switch cost can be almost neglected. Fig. 15 shows the results considering the base values in Table 2, where the battery cost accounts for more than 80 %. It is observed that the configurations with MPC and centralised battery (CB-MPC3, CB-MPC3f and CB-MPC2) show slightly lower battery costs in scenarios with unbalanced generation due to a lower energy capacity, as presented in Section 4.3.

Figure 15: Investment for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 2

Although investment is significantly high, benefits from the curtailment reduction of renewable generation must be considered to provide a complete economic evaluation. The payback time is used to consider both the investment and curtailment reduction contributions. Two different payback times are considered in the economic analysis: payback respect to Ref and payback respect to DB.

The payback time results respect to the Reference configuration conclude that scenarios with feeder interconnection are the options that can mainly provide reasonable times compared with the lifetime of the components. Fig. 16 shows the results considering the base values in Table 2, where the payback time is lower than 20 years for all scenarios and configurations with feeder interconnections.

Figure 16: Payback respect to Ref for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 2

If the payback time is evaluated considering that the distributed batteries are already in place, the results are not only economically feasible but also very attractive. Fig. 17 shows the results considering the base values in Table 2, where the payback time is lower than 20 years for all scenarios and in particular lower than 4 years for scenarios 2 and 3. Configurations with switch interconnection (DB-S) have a payback time almost equal to zero due to the low cost of the switch components. However, it should be mentioned that configurations with MPC provide higher operation flexibility compared to a simple switch interconnection. Then, their payback time could be further reduced if the contribution of additional grid services were considered in the economic analysis.

Figure 17: Payback respect to DB for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 2

Equivalent result trends are obtained considering the additional values of the sensitivity analysis parameters, but are not shown for simplicity. Even when the sizing and annual renewable generation results are approximately independent of the cost and energy prize variations considered in Table 2, as commented before, the payback time is highly affected.

Then, the payback time respect to Ref is further analysed with expressions in relation to cost parameters and energy prize. Linear regressions are derived for the expressions of the cost parameters. In particular, the regressions are obtained with a coefficient of determination R^2 close to 1.

The impact of the battery cost variation on the payback time variation is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta PBT &= k_{bat} \cdot \Delta C_{cap} \\ k_{bat} &= \begin{cases} 0.81 - 0.91 & \text{if there is MPC} \\ 0.941 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

where ΔPBT and ΔC_{cap} are the percentage variations of the payback time and battery cost. In general, battery cost variations highly affect the payback, as observed from k_{bat} , which has different values depending on the configuration.

The impact of converter cost variation (for battery and MPC) on the payback time variation is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta PBT &= k_{conv} \cdot \Delta C_{conv} \\ k_{conv} &= \begin{cases} 0.059 & \text{if there is no MPC} \\ 0.9 - 1 & \text{if there is MPC but no batteries} \\ 0.12 - 0.19 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

where ΔC_{conv} is the percentage variation of the converter cost. In this case, the converter cost has a low influence on the payback time, as observed from k_{conv} , except when the only element considered is the multiport.

When there is no MPC or its sizing is not affected by the annual energy price, then the total system cost remains invariable. In this case, annual energy price impact has been analysed based on an expression that can be directly derived from equation (37):

$$\Delta PBT = \frac{1}{1 + \Delta C_{en}} - 1 \quad (45)$$

where ΔC_{en} is the percentage variation of the annual energy price. Configurations with MPC of scenarios 2 and 3 have low sizing variability, therefore the energy price impact on them can be explained with small deviations from equation (37). On the other hand, configurations with MPC of scenario 1 have significant variability as explained in Section 4.4, therefore the energy price impact is significantly higher than shown in equation (45), especially when the energy price is reduced. Overall, it is clear that this price has a significant impact on the payback time.

4.8. Scenario with 25 % generation reduction

The initial scenario considers a significantly high penetration of renewable generation. A 25 % reduction of generation installed capacity is considered in this section in order to analyse the effect on the MPC sizing and performance results.

In this case, a larger battery is needed due to the island requirement of the battery sizing method, and the MPC size is already discussed in Section 4.4. As a consequence, the investment increases increase due to the larger battery cost. Annual generation and curtailment are reduced, as seen in Fig. 18 and 19. Moreover, the curtailment is significantly lower than in the initial scenario, therefore differences in the annual generation between the configurations are less evident.

Figure 18: Annual generation for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 2 and 25 % reduction of installed generation capacity

Figure 19: Curtailment for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 2 and 25 % reduction of installed generation capacity

The payback time presents a significant increase due to the reduction of income from the sold renewable energy and the increase in battery costs, as seen in Fig. 20. In this case, only scenario 3 would be feasible in all interconnection configurations. While in scenarios 1 and 2, only the multiport acting as a soft open point without batteries in the system would have a payback time respect to Ref lower or similar to the lifetime of the converter (20-25 years). If the batteries were already in the system, the multiport would be economically feasible in almost all configurations, as shown in Fig. 21. Sometimes, even reaching higher benefits with lower costs, because the centralised battery is smaller than the distributed one. In Fig. 21, the payback is not clearly seen in some configurations (DB-S, CB-MPC3 and CB-MPC2) because it is close to zero years.

Figure 20: Payback respect to Ref for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 2 and 25 % reduction of installed generation capacity

Figure 21: Payback respect to DB for each scenario and configuration, considering the base values of Table 2 and 25 % reduction of installed generation capacity

If a 50 % reduction of generation installed capacity is considered, these trends are followed but with more extreme values. In general, the results of this case show that only payback time respect to DB in scenario 3 would be lower than 20 years.

Therefore, the MPC application in this case study is only feasible for scenarios with high generation or if the generation is unbalanced between feeders and the batteries are assumed to be initially installed in the system.

5. Conclusion

This paper analysed the multiport converter as a potential solution to reduce generation curtailment in distribution grids with a high penetration of renewables. A general methodology was presented to size the required multiport converter based on an optimisation problem with electrical constraints. This methodology also provides technical and economic indicators for a complete evaluation of the multiport converter integration.

The general methodology was validated to size a three-terminal multiport converter with and without battery terminals in a case study inspired by the medium voltage CIGRE benchmark network. The results concluded that in scenarios with unbalanced distributed generation in the feeders, the rated power of the multiport converter terminals used to exchange power between different feeders was sized with a relatively constant value similar to the nominal power of the system, around 25 MVA. Whereas in scenarios with balanced distributed generation in the feeders, the size of the rated power of the multiport converter terminals depends on the interconnection configuration and economic parameters.

This case study was also used to compare the multiport converter solution to alternative configurations with separated batteries and a simple switch interconnection. As a general conclusion, the results showed that the multiport converter provides clear advantages and is economically viable. In particular, the multiport converter can reduce power curtailment in equivalent terms or even better than battery solutions, especially in scenarios with unbalanced distributed generation in the feeders. In these scenarios, feeder interconnection can increase renewable generation more than 15 % while the battery only provides 5 % improvements. From an economical point of view, all scenarios with high renewable penetration are feasible to install a multiport converter, as the payback of the investment is lower than 20 years. If renewable penetration is reduced, scenarios with unbalanced generation are the most economically feasible. Scenarios with balanced generation are not economically viable unless batteries are initially installed in the feeders. In general, for all scenarios, a multiport converter with a centralised battery is the best option. Configuration with a switch interconnection could provide similar economical results compared to the multiport converter options. However, the multiport converter has improvement margin since additional grid support services can be provided and are not evaluated in this paper.

The proposed planning methodology employs a deterministic approach.

Considering the long time horizon involved, future studies including uncertainties through stochastic or robust approaches could improve the outcomes of the planning methodology. Only steady-state analysis is performed and stability issues are not addressed. However, it is important to ensure that the power system will remain stable as renewable generation increases and also when the multiport converter and the battery are introduced. Also, future works can include the optimisation of battery and MPC location, as well as consider other functionalities and economic benefits of the multiport converter.

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Appendix A. Network parameters

The network parameters considered for the lines and transformers are shown in Tables A.4 and A.5 respectively. It should be mentioned that line segment 13 will only be considered if the switch is closed. Also, line segments 14 and 15 will only be considered if there is a multiport converter. When considering the multiport converter, buses 16 and 17 are equivalent to its AC ports, and the line segments between those buses and the feeders have in total the same length as the line segment of the original switch.

Table A.4: Connections and line parameters

Line segment	Node from	Node to	R'_{ph} [Ω/km]	X'_{ph} [Ω/km]	B'_{ph} [$\mu S/\text{km}$]	l [km]
1	1	2	0.501	0.716	47.493	2.82
2	2	3	0.501	0.716	47.493	4.42
3	3	4	0.501	0.716	47.493	0.61
4	4	5	0.501	0.716	47.493	0.56
5	5	6	0.501	0.716	47.493	1.54
6	7	8	0.501	0.716	47.493	1.67
7	8	9	0.501	0.716	47.493	0.32
8	9	10	0.501	0.716	47.493	0.77
9	10	11	0.501	0.716	47.493	0.33
10	3	8	0.501	0.716	47.493	1.3
11	12	13	0.510	0.366	3.172	4.89
12	13	14	0.510	0.366	3.172	2.99
13	14	8	0.510	0.366	3.172	2
14	14	17	0.510	0.366	3.172	0.8
15	8	16	0.510	0.366	3.172	1.2

Table A.5: Transformer parameters

Node from	Node to	Connection	V_1 [kV]	V_2 [kV]	Z_{tr} to V_2 side [Ω]	S_{rated} [MVA]
15	1	3-ph Dyn1	110	20	0.016+j1.92	25
15	12	3-ph Dyn1	110	20	0.016+j1.92	25

Appendix B. Load profiles

Load profiles are defined based on load information from six nearby towns in central Catalonia, as shown in Fig. B.22: Igualada, Rubió, Òdena, Castellfollit del Boix, Aguilar de Segarra, and Els Prats de Rei. It has been extracted residential hourly consumption of each city for one year, specifically for 2019, using Datadis which is a database of the Spanish electrical demand [37]. Since the load information is only for active power, reactive power demand is also included considering a power factor of 0.97.

Different loads are connected at each bus of the case study considering the load profile of the mentioned towns. In particular, the load profile of each town is considered as a base value, such that each node has a total load proportional to the base profile of a specific town. Fig. B.23 shows an example of the load profile of the towns for one week, where it can be seen that the towns have quite different profiles. Table B.6 presents the load distribution in each node as a multiplicative factor of the towns' load profiles. This distribution is arbitrarily selected in order to have a comparable demand while ensuring that the grid structure is adequate.

Figure B.22: Location of load and generation profiles

Figure B.23: Demands during a week

Table B.6: Load distribution

Node	Igualada	Rubió	Òdena	Castellfollit del Boix	Aguilar de Segarra	Els Prats de Rei
1	0	0	0	0	6	0
2	0	3	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0	0	3
5	0	0	0	5	0	0
6	0	0	0	6	0	0
7	0	0	0.5	0	0	0
8	0	0	0.6	0	0	0
9	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0	0	2
11	0	0	0	0	5	0
12	0.2	0	0	0	0	0
13	0.1	0	0	0	0	0
14	0.2	0	0	0	0	0

Appendix C. Generation profiles and scenarios

Solar photovoltaic and wind power are considered as distributed generation of the system. Generation profiles are defined based on resource information around the area where the towns are located. The generation information is obtained for a year, specifically for 2019, from *Renewable.ninja* [38], which is a website tool to obtain PV and wind generation profiles in any location. In particular, the generation profiles are obtained for the installed power of each node.

Table C.7 shows the generation distribution based on the installed capacity power for each scenario explained in Section 4.1. The total PV and wind generation installed in all scenarios is approximately the same to ensure a fair comparison. Furthermore, both load and generation data were distributed arbitrarily along the network so that the scenarios would have grid problems such as overvoltages, undervoltages and lines' saturation.

Table C.7: Scenario definition based on generation distribution

Nodes	Scenario 1		Scenario 2		Scenario 3	
	PV [MWp]	Wind [MW]	PV [MWp]	Wind [MW]	PV [MWp]	Wind [MW]
1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	34	46	4	46	40	56
4	34	0	4	0	40	0
5	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	0	50	0
8	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	0	2	0	52	0	40
10	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	0	0	20	0	0	0
13	60	54	60	4	18	16
14	0	0	30	0	0	0

Appendix D. Representative days selection

In this case study the representative days are selected according to the difference between the total generation and load profiles. First, different levels of load, PV and wind power availability are defined. To do so, one or more representative magnitudes that describe the profile have to be determined. The levels correspond to a range of values of these representative magnitudes so that there are both extremes and some middle values. The detailed definition of these levels depends on the case study.

The load profile trend is similar for different days, as during the night the load is low and there can appear some peaks during the day corresponding to dinner time and at first hour in the morning. Therefore, the maximum load has been supposed as a representative magnitude, which has been divided into 5 levels. For the PV power availability profile, most of the days have a similar profile since having shadows is not so common. Therefore, it has been supposed that the maximum power generation is a representative magnitude, which has been divided into 4 levels. On the other hand, the wind power

availability profile is quite variable. Its uncertain nature makes that, specially on days with significant wind power, the high wind power can appear for most of the day or only during a few hours. Therefore both the hourly maximum power generation and the total daily generation have been taken into account, and have been divided into different levels. Table D.8 shows the different levels considered for each magnitude.

Table D.8: Classification levels considered to select the representative days

max Load [MW]	max P_{PV} [$\frac{MW}{MWp}$]	max P_{wind} [$\frac{MW}{MW\ installed}$]	daily E_{wind} [$\frac{MWh}{MW\ installed}$]
<14.5	<0.3	<0.2	<4
14.5-16.5	0.3-0.6	0.2-0.4	4-9
16.5-21.5	0.6-0.8	0.4-0.7	9-14
21.5-26.5	>0.8	>0.7	>14
>26.5			

Then, all possible combinations between power levels of different profiles are considered. Each of those combinations can be seen as a type of day, resulting in a list. Afterwards, each day of the year is classified as one of those types according to its profiles. For each type of day, a weight w can be defined as equal to the percentage of days it contains over the total amount of days considered, which is 365 for one year.

Finally, the representative day types are those with percentages w higher than 2.5 %. From each of those day types, a single day is selected. The days selected are the representative days. At this step, it should be taken into account that the selected days must have different power profiles. It should be tried as well that the selected days are from different seasons and days of the week, and that they are around the middle value of their levels.

As a result, a total of 15 representative days are selected for the multiport converter sizing. Table D.9 shows the days selected and the weight of their type. Table D.10 shows the detailed levels of the representative day types. Fig. D.24 shows the profiles of the representative days and considering scenario 2, Fig. D.25 is obtained.

Table D.9: Representative days selected and their weights

Representative day	Calendar day	Weight [%]
1	January 8	4.1
2	January 24	2.7
3	February 15	4.4
4	February 16	2.5
5	March 4	2.5
6	April 10	18.1
7	May 3	4.1
8	June 25	5.8
9	July 4	6.8
10	August 11	9.6
11	August 19	3.6
12	September 15	2.5
13	October 18	3.0
14	December 23	2.5
15	December 27	2.5

Table D.10: Representative days classification levels

Representative day	max Load [MW]	max P_{PV} [$\frac{MW}{MWp}$]	max P_{wind} [$\frac{MW}{MW \text{ installed}}$]	daily E_{wind} [$\frac{MWh}{MW \text{ installed}}$]
1	21.5-26.5	0.6-0.8	0.4-0.7	4-9
2	21.5-26.5	0.6-0.8	>0.7	>14
3	21.5-26.5	0.6-0.8	<0.2	<4
4	16.5-21.5	0.6-0.8	<0.2	<4
5	16.5-21.5	0.6-0.8	>0.7	9-14
6	16.5-21.5	0.6-0.8	0.2-0.4	<4
7	16.5-21.5	0.3-0.6	<0.2	<4
8	16.5-21.5	0.6-0.8	0.4-0.7	9-14
9	21.5-26.5	0.6-0.8	0.2-0.4	<4
10	<14.5	0.6-0.8	0.2-0.4	<4
11	14.5-16.5	0.6-0.8	0.2-0.4	4-9
12	<14.5	0.6-0.8	0.4-0.7	9-14
13	16.5-21.5	0.3-0.6	0.2-0.4	<4
14	14.5-16.5	0.6-0.8	>0.7	9-14
15	14.5-16.5	0.6-0.8	<0.2	<4

Figure D.24: Demand (top), PV and wind power availability (bottom) on the representative days

Figure D.25: Load and generation of the system at the representative days in scenario 2

Appendix E. Battery sizing results

This section shows the numerical results of the battery sizing. Precisely, energy capacity and active power required for the batteries in each scenario

and considering distributed or centralised options, for the cases of the sensitivity analysis presented in Section 4.2 are presented in Table E.11.

Table E.11: Battery sizing results

(a) Battery size for 1h island mode

	Distributed				Centralised	
	P_A [MW]	$E_{cap,A}$ [MWh]	P_B [MW]	$E_{cap,B}$ [MWh]	P_{A+B} [MW]	$E_{cap,A+B}$ [MWh]
Scenario 1	12.12	16.84	6.06	8.41	17.97	24.95
Scenario 2	11.27	15.65	8.63	12	17.97	24.95
Scenario 3	10.78	14.97	7.62	10.59	17.73	24.64

(b) Battery size for 3h island mode

	Distributed				Centralised	
	P_A [MW]	$E_{cap,A}$ [MWh]	P_B [MW]	$E_{cap,B}$ [MWh]	P_{A+B} [MW]	$E_{cap,A+B}$ [MWh]
Scenario 1	12.12	48.57	6.06	24.24	17.97	72.4
Scenario 2	11.27	44.65	8.63	35.12	17.97	72.4
Scenario 3	10.78	43.55	7.62	30.93	17.73	71.67

(c) Battery size for 2h island mode when installed generation is reduced 25 %

	Distributed				Centralised	
	P_A [MW]	$E_{cap,A}$ [MWh]	P_B [MW]	$E_{cap,B}$ [MWh]	P_{A+B} [MW]	$E_{cap,A+B}$ [MWh]
Scenario 1	12.61	34.58	6.51	17.65	18.96	52.55
Scenario 2	12.10	32.53	8.78	24.25	19.04	52.55
Scenario 3	11.46	31.07	7.91	21.84	18.62	51.96

(d) Battery size for 2h island mode when installed generation is reduced 50 %

	Distributed				Centralised	
	P_A [MW]	$E_{cap,A}$ [MWh]	P_B [MW]	$E_{cap,B}$ [MWh]	P_{A+B} [MW]	$E_{cap,A+B}$ [MWh]
Scenario 1	13.10	35.77	6.96	18.81	19.95	55.43
Scenario 2	12.93	34.52	8.93	24.83	20.11	55.43
Scenario 3	12.14	32.73	8.20	22.78	19.51	55.18

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